

ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION LEARNING INNOVATION DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY-BASED

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Abstract

The advancement of science and technology has brought about an era where science, technology, and information are inseparable from education. This reality requires Islamic higher education institutions to effectively implement learning management practices. This research adopts a qualitative approach with a literature review method. The findings of this study reveal that the utilization of digital technology in Islamic Religious Education enhances the quality of learning and student engagement. Lecturers play a crucial role in developing the necessary skills and knowledge. Innovation in digital technology-based learning involves the discovery, development, and dissemination of digital technology usage. Digital content, curriculum design, lecturer training, and supportive infrastructure are essential in the development of digital technology. Digital technology enhances student engagement and learning effectiveness, yet the role of lecturers remains vital as facilitators and learning managers.

Keywords: Learning Innovation, Digital Technology, Islamic Religious Education

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is the century of knowledge, technology and information. One of the impacts of the development of technology on education and teaching of Islam in higher education, that the learning process can not be separated from digital technology (Suroso et al., 2021). In 2020 the whole world was hit by the Covid-19 pandemic, but learning must continue. Therefore, technology is the only hope so that education does not stop (Talkah & Muslih, 2021). In the digital era that continues to evolve, the pandemic situation that has permeated the campus makes the use of technology such as devices and several internet-based applications such as zoom, google meet an obligation on students. Gawai no longer serves as an entertainment media, but a medium for learning and working, namely designing programs and teaching materials. One of them is designing Islamic religious teaching materials in universities (Khojir et al., 2021).

In the current Era of information and communication technology, it is important to integrate ICT in learning activities, especially in designing Islamic religious education materials in universities to improve the quality of learning. Information technology develops along with the development of theory, communication, and technology that support the practice of learning activities. Computer based learning (CBL), web based learning (e-learning) is a form of ICT utilization that needs to be applied in education today

(Ramli, 2022).

The rapid development of technology brings significant changes in various aspects of life, including in the field of Education. Advances in digital technology have influenced changes in the education system, where the education system that used to rely only on books and promote monotonous memorization. As a result, learning can sometimes feel boring for students because it is centered on the role of lecturers. However, currently learning can utilize technology so that student interaction with learning materials can be more thorough. Learning by using technology is able to accommodate a variety of student learning abilities so as to improve their learning outcomes (Tekege, 2017).

Utilization of technology can create conducive learning conditions, because technology can facilitate and accelerate the task of students and improve their skills in utilizing technological advances (Suryadi, 2007). Therefore, innovation in education becomes important, because innovation is the development of knowledge to create or improve new processes or systems with significant (Chehade et al., 2020). Meanwhile, according to Rusdiana (2014) innovation is also related to modernization, where modernization can occur through the emergence of innovation in society, both in economics, politics, education, health, science, and technology.

The concept of digital learning is a form of innovation that cannot be separated from the role of technology. Technology facilitates all needs in the teaching and learning process. As according to Salsabila et al., (2020), digital technology in educational institutions serves as a support tool in learning, both to access learning information sources and to support learning activities and tasks. With the development of increasingly advanced technology, there are currently many platforms that can help the implementation of online learning.

In designing Islamic Religious Education Innovations based on digital technology, a strategic way is needed to help deliver learning materials to students. This is why the innovation of Islamic Religious Education must be designed based on digital technology, because digital technology has been widely used in various ways because of its ability to reproduce and develop learning capabilities. In addition, the existence of technology is related to education, because technology can provide more attention and thought compared to conventional learning design solutions (Duhaney, 2012).

However, the perfect integration of technology in higher education innovation is still a major challenge in all developed or developing countries (Chand et al., 2020). Research Latchem et al., (2008) showed that structural and cultural factors play an important role in the adoption of educational innovations in colleges. In this regard, organizational culture has a significant influence on the process of educational innovation. Educational innovation researchers argue that the institutional environment is a key factor influencing the success of learning innovation (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Organizational culture can be a driver for educational innovation, but it can also be an obstacle if it is not well managed. Therefore, educational institutions play an important role in identifying emerging organizational culture features and their impact on the adoption of learning innovations.

The relationship between Islamic religious education innovation with digital technology there is some previous research. As in the research Ambarwati et al., (2021) affirms that innovation is an important process of change and renewal in the world of education in order to keep up with developments in other areas. The use of technology has both positive and negative impacts. To minimize dampak negatifnya, good cooperation is needed from all parties so that the technology is used in accordance with the desired goals. The role of innovation in education is very important, especially in digital technology-based learning. Innovation is needed so that the use of digital technology can be done optimally and thoroughly. It is expected that all elements of society support and cooperate in optimizing educational innovation based on digital technology. With the presence of technology today, it is expected that lecturers and other educational actors can make good use of it.

Further research Maryam et al., (2020) highlights that the progress of innovation in audiovisual media, it is expected that students can better understand Islamic religious education materials and bring a new atmosphere to the learning process. This study shows that with the development of technology, access to audiovisual media in learning becomes easier. One of the most popular sites to access audiovisual media is YouTube. The role of educators in playing learning videos as mentors is very important. By using this media, can be formed a better learning effectiveness for students. In another perspective, Yumarni, (2019) pointed out that religious education is a course that is mandatory at the national level with the aim of achieving the formation of a student's personality as a whole (kaffah). One of the dominant innovations in Islamic religious education is development, which is a form of renewal that requires further development. However, this innovation is still not able to reach a large scale. The innovation was carried out with the aim of overcoming various problems in the field of Education. In conclusion, the use of Information Technology in Islamic Religious Education Learning Innovation in higher education needs to be developed and improved in order to provide optimal results. Research that highlights the advantages and disadvantages of learning using digital media is stated by Rosyad (2019) one of the advantages is that students can learn about teaching materials anytime and anywhere if needed, because teaching materials are stored in computers. However, one of the disadvantages is the reduced interaction between faculty and students or even between students themselves. Therefore, the expected result of learning Islamic Religious Education is to have competencies that are in accordance with the needs of stakeholders, which include professional needs, social needs, industrial needs, and aspects of scientific vision. Thus, this nation has skilled human resources and is able to compete both locally and internationally.

Based on several literature reviews, it basically pays attention to the importance of Pai learning based on digital technology. Therefore, this study will provide emphasis and different perspectives related to Pai learning innovation using digital technology. Basically this study aims to understand the innovation of Islamic Religious Education Teaching based on digital technology. Therefore, the formulation of the question in this research is how to innovate Islamic Religious Education Teaching based on digital technology.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses qualitative methods with a literature review approach. Literature review is a research method that involves collecting data from various library sources, such as books, notes, research reports from journals, and others. In this method, researchers conduct a review of several libraries in order to collect the required data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Utilization of Digital technology in PAI learning

In the context of Islamic Religious Education Learning, lecturers have a very important role in determining the success of learning. In the development of digital technology, lecturers must have sufficient skills to utilize the technology effectively. Lecturers who have good professional competence have a significant influence on student achievement. Therefore, in the development of digital technology, lecturers need to develop the skills and knowledge needed to utilize the technology in learning Islamic Religious Education.

These professional competencies include an understanding of relevant digital technologies, the utilization of digital learning tools, and the ability to design and implement effective learning using technology. Lecturers also need to be ready to face changes that occur in the development of digital technology.

Digital technology continues to develop rapidly, so lecturers must constantly update their knowledge and skills in accordance with the latest developments. Lecturers who are flexible and open to change can more easily adopt digital technology in Islamic Religious Education Learning. Lecturers need to have skills in delivering interesting teaching so that students can better understand learning.

In the context of digital technology development, lecturers need to think about strategies and learning methods that are in accordance with the use of technology. This includes the selection of appropriate tools and applications, the preparation of interesting material, and the use of active interaction between lecturers and students through digital technology. Despite technological advances, the role of lecturers in teaching remains irreplaceable.

Digital technology provides new opportunities for lecturers to engage students in critical thinking activities and interactive learning. Lecturers remain facilitators, directors, and motivators in the learning process of Islamic Religious Education, while digital technology becomes a supportive tool in achieving learning goals.

The use of digital technology in Islamic Religious Education, the steps of developing learning content using digital technology will have a positive impact.

Here are some of the benefits that can be obtained in the use of digital technology in Islamic Religious Education, namely:

- a. The use of digital technology, such as mobile applications, online learning platforms, or interactive multimedia, can increase student engagement in learning Islamic Religious Education. Students can learn the material in a more interesting and interactive way, thus generating interest and higher learning motivation.
- b. With the use of digital technology, lecturers can present richer Islamic Religious Education Learning content, such as learning videos, audio, interactive simulations, and online information sources. This can help students understand religious concepts visually and audibly, as well as provide access to more extensive and reliable resources.
- c. The use of digital technology in learning Islamic Religious Education provides opportunities for students to develop technology skills needed in the digital age. They can learn to use various applications, operate digital devices, and make wise use of the internet. These skills will benefit students in their daily lives and prepare them for a future that is increasingly dependent on technology.
- d. Digital technology allows learning Islamic Religious Education can be done flexibly and can be accessed from anywhere. Students can access learning materials, assignments, and other resources through online learning platforms, mobile applications, or websites that have been provided. This provides flexibility for students to study according to the time and place they choose, making it easier for them to manage their study time.
- e. The use of digital technology also allows students to collaborate and communicate with fellow students, lecturers, and Islamic religious experts inside and outside the educational environment. They can participate in online discussion forums, virtual group work, or contact Islamic lecturers and religious experts to ask questions or get additional guidance. This opens up opportunities to expand students' understanding of Islam through interaction and discussion with others.

In implementing the use of digital technology in Islamic religious education, it is important for lecturers to have an understanding of relevant technology, master the skills of using technology, and have the ability to design and develop learning content that is in accordance with the learning objectives and values of the Islamic religion. Thus, the use of digital technology in Islamic religious education can provide a more fun, interactive, and effective learning experience for students.

Digital technology in Islamic Religious Education has an important role in solving educational problems and improving the learning process. This is because it is not only related to learning techniques and methods, but also involves the use of digital technology as a facilitator and support in learning. In addition, digital technology can also play a Supporting Role in the existing learning system. In the context of Islamic Religious Education, digital technology can be used to present learning materials in an interesting

and interactive way. For example, the use of multimedia, video, or mobile applications that enrich the student's learning experience.

The application of digital technology also has an impact on increasing the effectiveness of PAI learning. By utilizing technology, lecturers can deliver learning materials more efficiently and interactively, so that students can be more involved and understand the material better. However, it is important to remember that digital technology is only a tool or means in the PAI learning process. The role of permanent lecturers is very important as facilitators and learning managers. Lecturers have a key role in designing learning that suits student needs, supervising the proper use of digital technology, and ensuring learning goals are achieved.

Designing Pai learning innovations

Innovation can be interpreted as a new change that aims to make improvements or create something different from what has existed before, done deliberately and planned. In the context of learning technology, innovation refers to the use of advanced technology, both software and hardware, in the learning process. The application of this new technology aims to improve the quality, effectiveness and efficiency of learning. Learning methods and strategies are also part of the innovations that continue to be developed by actors in the world of Education.

For example, in schools, innovation is carried out in learning Islamic religious materials by utilizing information technology. For example, using internet services available in schools as a support for learners to improve their understanding of Islamic religious material. One form of innovation is to adopt web-based learning (Web Enhanced Course) that uses the internet as a means of support in teaching and learning activities in the classroom.

In addition, innovation can also be done through various approaches, including the use of games and educational applications that support the distance learning process by utilizing internet technology access. Thus, innovations in learning technology can open up opportunities to improve student learning experiences, expand access to educational resources, and optimize the overall learning process.

In this digital era, innovation continues to evolve to create learning that is more effective, interactive, and relevant to the needs of learners. Innovation in learning technology also provides benefits in increasing student involvement in the learning process. By using advanced technologies such as interactive learning software or hardware that support learning activities, students can actively engage in material exploration, collaborate with fellow students, and participate in more engaging learning activities. In addition, innovations in learning methods and strategies also provide new approaches to teaching and learning materials. Lecturers can use more creative and diverse approaches, such as flipped classroom, blended learning, or project-based learning, which allow students to actively engage in the learning process and develop skills relevant to future needs.

With online learning apps and platforms, students can stay connected with lecturers and fellow students, access learning materials flexibly, and participate in discussions and assignments virtually. This provides an opportunity to continue the learning process without having to be in the same physical environment. However, it is important to remember that innovation in learning technology must also be accompanied by careful planning, training for educators, and effective management. The use of technology in learning must take into account the needs and characteristics of students, as well as ensuring the security and privacy of data in the use of technology.

Innovation Model in Islamic religious education can be seen in several stages, namely *First*, the invention (Invention) at this stage involves the creation or discovery of new things. The renewal that occurs in education often results in different changes than before. This discovery can occur both inside and outside an educational institution, such as a school or college. Many hardware-based innovations come from sources outside educational institutions. However, there are also discoveries made within educational institutions by lecturers who seek to change the situation or create new ways to solve existing problems.

Second, development at the development stage involves the process of developing and expanding innovations that cannot yet be applied on a large scale. Development is often related to research, and involves activities such as basic research to find and test learning theories. At this stage, an expert team of curriculum program authors at an educational institution or college is involved in developing a new curriculum that will then be tested. In addition, evaluative research design is also made to assess the effectiveness of various curriculum updates.

Third, the spread (diffusion), at the stage of dissemination is often used synonymously with the concept of dissemination (dissemination), but in this context has a different connotation. Diffusion can be defined as "the spread of a new idea from the source of the invention to the final recipient" according to the Diffusion of Innovations theory proposed by Everett Rogers. At this stage, the innovations that have been developed will be disseminated to end users or recipients, such as lecturers or students, through various mechanisms such as training, publication, or introduction to learning activities.

At the invention stage, innovation in Islamic Religious Education Learning based on digital technology includes the creation or invention of various applications, software, or digital learning platforms specifically designed to support Islamic Religious Education Learning. For example, the development of mobile applications that can be downloaded on smartphone devices to help students learn the verses of the Quran interactively. This kind of application may provide features such as verse translation, verse reading audio, commentary, or quizzes to test student understanding. In addition, innovation can also include the development of interactive applications that allow students to interact with Islamic Religious Education learning materials virtually. For example, applications that present simulations or interactive games to understand religious concepts, such as recognizing animals in the universe or navigating stories in the Quran through the use of graphics, animations, and other interactive features. The creation or invention of these

specialized applications, software or digital learning platforms opens up new opportunities to enrich the learning of Islamic Religious Education in a more engaging and interactive way. Students can have access to relevant digital resources, explore material more interactively, and develop a deeper understanding of religious concepts through the use of digital technology.

In the development stage, Islamic Religious Education Learning Innovation based on digital technology involves the expansion and development of the use of digital technology in the context of Islamic Religious Education Learning. The development stage involves the creation of rich and varied digital content for Islamic Religious Education Learning. This can include the development of engaging learning videos, interactive multimedia, web-based learning modules, or e-books that students can access online. This digital content provides greater accessibility and can increase student engagement in Islamic Religious Education Learning. Innovation development also involves curriculum design that is integrated with digital technology. The curriculum should consider the use of digital technology as an effective learning tool and pay attention to the development of student skills in the use of technology. In addition, curriculum design should also include innovative learning methods that optimize the use of technology, such as Project-Based Learning, online collaboration, or interactive simulations. The development phase also involves the use of technology-based evaluation tools to measure student progress and understanding. For example, the use of a learning management system (LMS) equipped with online evaluation tools, such as interactive quizzes, online assignments, or computer-based exams. This evaluation tool can provide fast and accurate feedback to students and lecturers to monitor student learning progress.

In the diffusion stage, Islamic Religious Education Learning Innovation based on digital technology involves the introduction and dissemination of the use of digital technology in Islamic Religious Education Learning to lecturers and students widely. The deployment phase involves training lecturers in the use of digital technology for Islamic Religious Education Learning. Lecturers need to be given adequate training to understand and use digital tools, online learning platforms, and relevant applications in the context of the Islamic religion. This training can be done through workshops, seminars, or other professional development programs. This stage also involves the dissemination of information about applications and learning platforms available in Islamic Religious Education Learning. This information can be provided through seminars, workshops, publications, or online learning portals. The aim is to introduce various digital resources that can be used by lecturers and students in learning Islamic Religious Education. Then it requires the development of infrastructure that supports access to digital technology in the educational environment. This includes the availability of stable and fast internet access, the presence of adequate technological devices, and a learning environment that supports the use of digital technology.

CONCLUSION

The study of Islamic Religious Education Learning Innovation based on digital technology, which focused on the design of Pai learning innovation, in its analysis resulted in the conclusion that the use of digital technology in Islamic Religious Education can improve the quality of learning and student engagement. Lecturers play a key role in developing the skills and knowledge necessary to make effective use of digital technology. Islamic Religious Education Learning Innovation based on digital technology involves the discovery, development, and dissemination of the use of digital technology in learning. The development of rich learning digital content, curriculum design integrated with digital technology, lecturer training, and supporting infrastructure are important steps in the development of digital technology in Islamic Religious Education. Digital technology can improve student engagement, access to resources, and learning effectiveness. However, it is important to remember that the role of lecturers as facilitators and learning managers cannot be replaced by digital technology.

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